

REPORT ON
SEED DIVERSITY, GERMINATION, PLANT STANDING AND HARVESTING
PART-I
KHARIF SEASON

State Name: BIHAR
Third Reintroduction of Farmer's Varieties
2022-2023

Fig.: Harvesting of Ghaghra Pulses; Passbook Number – 811303-01-0064 and 001

Submitted to
FAO, ITPGRFA IV CYCLE PROJECT

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Under the project
Improving pulse biodiversity in rice fallow areas of tribal belts of Central and East Indian states to bring resilience in the farming practice, provide livelihood support and enhance nutritional level of the tribal population

Seed Biodiversity Report

Time Period for Sowing: JUNE 2022

Sowing Season June 2022, BIHAR

Bihar, Re-Introduction of Crop June 2022

S.No.	Crop Name	Variety Name	Type of Variety	Seeds In Bank for Re-Intro	Seed destroyed / damaged in seed bank 2021-022	Seeds from Haat	Seed from Market /KVK	Purchase from farmer 022	Trial Plot and Reporting (Account No.)	Ditributed to Account No.	
	Arhar	Arhar	Shanti, Jiwa, Tuka	Hybrid (survey)	2	0	0	0	001, Hareram	0	
		Arhar	Sanjiv, Dilip	Local	0	1.5	0	0	0	0	
		Arhar	LRG 41	Improved	4	0	0	0	05, karmeli	12,13	
		Arhar	Ratan	Improved	6	0	0	6 kg	02, Jiva	4,5,9,82,83,84	
		Arhar	NTL 30	Improved	2	0	0	0	64 Pudi Soren	0	
	Ground Nut	Ground Nut	Jiva Soren	Local	0	0	0	0	5 Kg X 110 Rs = 550 rs	2	1,12,22
			Karmeli	Local	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			K6*	Improved	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			TG-37A*	Improved	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Urad / Black Gram	Urad	T9	Improved	2	0	0	0	0	2	0
			PU31*	Improved	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Moong	Moong	Jiva Soren,	Local	1	0	0	0	0	5	0
		Moong	Tuka Besra	Local	1	0	0	0	0	64	0
		Moong	IPM 25 / Virat	Improved	8	1.5	0	0	7kg (Hareram) x 100 Rs = 700 Rs	001,	16,10,9,6,24,23,26,22,5,20
		Moong	IPM 2-3	Improved	7	1	0	0	0	2	0
	Kudrum / Hibiscus cannabenus	Red Kudrum	Madhopur Haat	Local	4.5	0	0	0	0	64	12,18
		White Kudrum	Telwa Bazar	Local	4	0	0	0	5 Kg (Rekha Kisku) X 80 Rs = 400 Rs	5	13,19,20

	Ghagra / Vigna Sinensis	Ghagra	Telwa Haat	Local	3	1.5		0	0	0	1	2,5	
			Madhopur Haat	Local	2	1.5		0	0	0	64	8	
			Etwari (farmer)	Local	0.7	0		0	0	0	2	0	
			Sakina(Farmer)	Local	1	0		0	0	0	5	0	
	Maize	Maize Yellow/Golden	Kanchan KVK	Improved	4	0		0	2 kg	0	001,	15,33,34	
		Maize Yellow/Golden	Sarikar 2079 KVK	Improved	4	0		0	2 kg	0	002,	36,37,41,43	
		Maize White	Madhopur Haat	Local	3	0.5		0	0	5kg (Tuka) X 30 Rs = 150 Rs	64	57,59,61	
		Maize Yellow Desi	Telwa Haat	Local	3.5	0.5		0	0	0	5	62,63,65	
		Maize Red	Madhopur Haat	Local	4 kg	0.5		0	0	10 kg (Hareram) X 30 Rs = 300 Rs	12	71, 68,69,76, 85,86	
	Bajra	Bajra	KVK	Improved	4.5	0.5		0	0	0	12, Tuka Basera	64,01,59	
		Bajra	Telwa Haat	Local	2	0.5		0	0	0	64	18	
		Bajra	Madhopur Haat	Local	2	0.5		0	0	0	5	17	
	Ragi	Ragi	Madhopur Haat	Local	4.5	0		0	0	0	5 kg (Pudi Soren) X 60 Rs = 300 Rs	64	66,78
			VL 379	Improved	0	0		0	0	0	0	0	
				Total	75.7 Kg	10 kg			10 kg @ 2600 Rs. MR. parimal Ji's Account	37 Kg @ 2400 Rs. Mr. Upende r Kumar 's Account			

**Total Seed in Circulation in June =
75.7 kg + 10 kg+37 kg = 122.7 Kg**

Sowing Season August 2022, BIHAR

Bihar, Re-Introduction of Crop_August 2022

	Sesame/ Til	White Til	Kanke Safed*	Improved	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			Akash*	Improved	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			RT346*	Improved	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			RT351*	Improved	1	0	0	0	0		
		Black Til	Local	Local	5.5	0	0	0	5 Kg (Harera m) X 100 Rs = 500 Rs		
			Krishna	Improved	1	0	0	0	0		
		Red/ Brown Til	Vinod	Improved	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
			Rama	Improved	0	0	0	2 Kg X 300 Rs = 600 Rs	0		
	Niger/R amtil /Sarguja		Birsa Niger -1	Improved	3	0	0	0	0		
	Kulthi		Birsa Kulthi-1	Improved	0.6	0	0	0	0		
			Shiv lal	Local	0.75	0	0	0	0		
			Teknarayan	Local	0.5	0	0	0	0		
			Jai Kumar	Local	1.5	0	0	0	0		
			Chandan Haat	Local	5	0	0	0	10 kg X 80 Rs (Harera m) = 800 Rs		
			Jasidih Haat	Local	5	0	0	0	10 kg X 80 Rs (Pradip yadav) = 800 Rs.		

		TOTAL SEED		22.7 00 KG	25 kg Local and 2 KG KVK		
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Total Seed in circulation for September 022 sowing = 47.700 KG

Germination report:

Crop: Pearl Millet (Bajra)

Trials on farmer's field (A/c no. 005,012)

Passbook no	Crop Name	Variety	Sowing Date	Date of germination 50%	Any pest Attack	Water Logging	Other Vulnerable factor	Scientist suggestion
005	Bajra	Kvk	20/7/2022	28/7/2022	No	No	No	yes
012	Bajra	Telwahaat	23/7/2022	29/7/2022	No	No	No	

Crop: Ghanghra

Trials on farmer's field (A/c no. 001,002,064,005)

Passbook no	Crop Name	Variety	Sowing Date	Date of germination 50%	Any pest Attack	Water Logging	Other Vulnerable factor	Scientist suggestion
001`	Ghaghra	telwahaat	21/7/2022	29/7/2022	No	No	no	yes
002	Ghaghra	etwarimarandi	18/7/2022	28/7/2022	No	No	No	

005	Ghaghra	sakina bibi	17/7/2022	27/7/2022	No	No	No	
064	Ghaghra	madhopur haat	18/7/2022	25/7/2022	No	No	No	

A/c no 001; Image: Moong	A/c no 005; Image: Moong
A/c no 002; Image: Moong	A/c no 0064; Image: Moong

Crop: Groundnut

Trial on farmer's field (A/c no. 002)

Passbook no	Crop Name	Variety	Sowing Date	Date of germination 50%	Anypest Attack	Water Logging	Other Vulnerable factor	Scientist suggestion
002	Groundnut	Jiva soren	19/7/2022	29/7/2022	No	No	No	yes

Trail Plots at Jiva Soren

Trial on farmer's field (A/c no. 002)

Passbook no. 002	Crop Name	Variety	Sowing Date	Date of germination 50%	Anypest Attack	Water Logging	Other Vulnerable factor	Scientist suggestion
Trial 1	ARAHAR	RATAN	18/7/2022	29/7/2022	No	No	No	yes
Trial 2	Groundnut	Jiwa	18/7/2022	29/7/2022	No	No	No	
Trial 3	Urad	T9	18/7/2022	0%	No	No	No	
Trial 4	Moong	lpm2-3	18/7/2022	29/7/2022	No	No	NO	
Trial 5	Ghanghara	Etawari	18/7/2022	29/7/2022	No	No	No	
Trial 6	Maize	sarokar	18/7/2022	29/7/2022	no	No	no	

Trail farm no 1ka image	Trail farm no 1ka image

Crop: Maize

[Trials on farmer's field \(A/c no. 001,002,064,005,012\)](#)

Passbook no	Crop Name	Variety	Sowing Date	Date of germination 50%	Any pest Attack	Water Logging	Other Vulnerable factor	Scientist suggestion
001	Maize	Kvk kanchan	17/7/2022	24/7/2022	No	No	no	yes
002	Maize	Kvk sarokar	19/7/2022	26/7/2022	No	No	No	
064	Maize whire	Madhopur.haat	18/7/2022	28/7/2022	No	No	No	
005	Maize yellow	Telwahaat	14/7/2022	22/7/2022	No	No	No	
012	Maize red	Madhopur.haat	20/7/2022	27/7/2022	NO	No	NO	

A/c no 001 image maize		A/c no 005 image maize	
A/c no 064 image maize		A/c no 002 image maize	
A/c no 012 image maize			

Crop: moong

Trials on farmer's field (A/c no. 001,002,005,064)

Passbook no	Crop Name	Variety	Sowing Date	Date of germination 50%	Any pest Attack	Water Logging	Other Vulnerable factor	Scientist suggestion
001`	moong	IPM25	21/7/2022	29/7/2022	No	No	no	yes
002	Moong	IPM2-3	19/7/2	28/7/2022	No	No	No	

			022					
005	Moong	Jiva soren	20/7/2022	27/7/2022	No	No	No	
064	moong	Tuka besra	18/7/2022	26/7/2022	No	No	No	

Crop: Arhar

Trial on farmer's field (A/c no. 001,005,002,064)

Passbook.no	Crop Name	Variety	Sowing Date	Date of germination 50%	Any pest Attack	Water Logging	Other Vulnerable factor	Scientist suggestion
001	ARHAR	Santi jiva	17/7/2022	23/7/2022	No	No	no	yes

Trial 1	ARAHA R	Lrg 41	19/7/2022	28/7/2022	No	No	No	yes
Trial 2	Moong	Jiwa	19/7/2022	27/7/2022	No	No	No	
Trial 3	White kudrum	Telwahaat	19/7/2022	29/7/2022	No	No	No	
Trial 4	Ghanghra	Sakina bibi	19/7/2022	26/7/2022	No	No	NO	
Trial 5	Maize	Telwahaat	19/7/2022	28/7/2022	No	No	No	
Trial 6	Bazra	Madhopur haat	19/7/2022	27/7/2022	no	No	no	

Trail farm-2; Image: moong

Trail farm-4; Image: Ghaghra

Crop: White/Red/Kudrum

[Trials on farmer's field \(A/c no. 064,005\)](#)

Passbook no.	Crop Name	Variety	Sowing Date	Date of germination 50%	Any pest Attack	Water Logging	Other Vulnerable factor	Scientist suggestion
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0064	Red Kudrum	Modhopur haat	20/7/2022	28/7/2022	No	No	No	yes
005	White Kudrum	Telwa haat	19/7/2022	26/7/2022	No	No	No	yes

A/c no 005; Image: White Kudrum	A/c no 0064; Image: Red Kudrum

Crop: Ragi

Trial on farmer's field (A/c no. 064)

Passbook no	Crop Name	Variety	Sowing Date	Date of germination 50%	Any pest Attack	Water Logging	Other Vulnerable factor	Scientist suggestion
0064	Ragi	Modhopur haat	26/7/2022	29/7/2022	No	No	No	yes

A/c no 0064; Image: Ragi

Plant Standing Report:

Crop: ARHAR

Trials on farmer's field (A/c No. 001,005, 002,064)

Trial plot no. /pass book no.	Crop name and variety	No. of plants stand	% of plants with flower	Any disease observed in plants so far	Water logging	Contact with scientist	Other vulnerable factor
001	Arahar Santi,jiwa,tuka	60%	0	NO	No	yes	no
005	Arahar, IRG 41	55%	0	„	No	yes	
002	Arahar,ratan	60%	0	„	No	Yes	
0064	Arahar ,ntl 30	70%	0	„	No	Yes	

A/c no 002; Image Arhar	A/c no 001; Image Arhar
A/c no 005; Image: Arhar	A/c no 0064; Image: Arhar

Crop: Ghaghra

Trials on farmer's field (A/c No. 001,005, 002,064)

Trial plot no. /pass book no.	Crop name and variet Y	No. of plants stand	% of plants with flower	Any diseese observed in plants so far	Water logging	Contact with scientist	Other vulnerable factor
001	Ghaghra Telwa haat	60%	25%	Yes,leaf white	no	yes	no
002	Ghaghra Etwari marandi	70%	30%	„	No	yes	
005	Ghaghra Sakina bibi	80%	20%	„	No	Yes	
0064	Ghaghra Madhopur haat	75%	15%	„	No	Yes	

A/c no 001; Image: Ghaghra

A/c no 001; Image: Ghaghra

A/c no 005; Image: Ghaghra	A/c no 0064; Image: Ghaghra

Crop: Maize

Trials on farmer's field (A/c No. 012,005, 064)

Trial plot no. /pass book no.	Crop name and variet Y	No. of plants stand	% of plants with flower	Any diseese observed in plants so far	Water logging	Contact with scientist	Other vulnerable factor
005	Bazrz kvk	40%	0		No	yes	no
0012	Bazra telwa haat	35%	0		No	yes	
0064	Bazra madhopur	50%	0		No	Yes	

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A/c no 005; Image: Bajra		A/c no 0012; Image: Bajra	
A/c no 0064; Image: Bajra			

Crop: Groundnut

Trial on farmer's field (A/c No. 002)

Trial plot no. /pass book no.	Crop name and variety	No. of plants stand	% of plants with flower	Any disease observed in plants so far	Water logging	Contact with scientist	Other vulnerable factor	
002	groundnut jiwa soren	60%	25%	no	No	yes	no	

A/c no 002: Image sowing groundnut

Crop: Groundnut, Urad, Moong, Ghaghra, Arhar, Maize
Trials on farmer's field (Farmer Jiva Soren)

Trial plot no. /pass book no.	Crop name and variety	No. of plants stand	% of plants with flower	Any disease observed in plants so far	Water logging	Contact with scientist (y/N) Y Date required for scientist	Other vulnerable factor
Trial 1	Arahar, ratan	70%	0	no	No	yes	no

Trial 2	Groundnut.ji wa soren	45%	20%	„	No	yes		
Trial 3	Urad , t9	30%	10%	„	No	Yes		
Trial 4	Moong, ipm 2-3	60%	40%	„	No	Yes		
Trial 5	Ghaghra ,etwari	60%	30%	„				
Trial 6	Maize,sarokar	80%	20%	„				

farm no 1 ka image arhar

farm no 4 image moong

Crop: Groundnut, Urad, Moong, Ghaghra, Arhar, Maize
Trials on farmer's field (Farmer Karmeli Kisku)

Trial plot no. /pass book no.	Crop name and variet Y	No. of plants stand	% of plants with flower	Any diseas observed in plants so far	Water logging	Contact with scientist (y/N) Y Date required for scientist	Other vulnerable factor
Trial 1	Arahar, lrg 41	55%	0	No	No	yes	no
Trial 2	Moong, jiwa	60%	40%	,	No	yes	

Trial 3	White kudrum,telwa haat	50%	0	„	No	Yes	
Trial 4	Ghaghra ,sakina bibi	60%	40%	„	No	Yes	
Trial 5	Maize telwa haat	45%	35%	„	no		
Trial 6	Bajra madhopur	40%	0	„	no		

Trial 2; Image: Moong	Trial 5; Image: Ghaghra

Crop: Red/White Kudrum

Trials on farmer's field (064,005)

Trial plot no. /pass book no.	Crop name and variety	No. of plants stand	% of plants with flower	Any disease observed in plants so far	Water logging	Contact with scientist	Other vulnerable factor
064	Red kudrum madhopur,haat	70%	0	no	No	yes	no

005	White kudrum,telwa haat.	60%	0	no	no			
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Crop: Maize

Trials on farmer's field (001, 002,005,012,064)

Trial plot no. /pass book no.	Crop name and variety	No. of plants stand	% of plants with flower	Any disease observed in plants so far	Water logging	Contact with scientist	Other vulnerable factor
001	maize, kanchan	80%	30%	Life,insect	No	yes	no
002	Maize (Var. sarokar)	75%	40%	„	No	yes	
0064	Maize White (madhopur haat)	80%	35%	„	No	Yes	
005	Maize Yellow, (Telwa haat)	70%	50%	„	No	Yes	
0012	Maize Red (Madhopur Haat)	65%	40%	„			

A/c no 0012 image maize

A/c no 001 image maize

Ac no 002 image maize

ac no 0064 image maize

ac no 005 image maize

Crop: Moong

Trials on farmer's field (001, 002,005,012,064)

Trial plot no. /pass book no.	Crop name and variety	No. of plants stand	% of plants with flower	Any disease observed in plants so far	Water logging	Contact with scientist	Other vulnerable factor
001	Moong, IPM 25	75%	30%	Yes (Leaf, white)	no	yes	no
002	Moong Ipm2-3	65%	35%		No	yes	
005	Moong Jiwa soren	80%	40%	„	No	Yes	
0064	Moong Tuka besra	85%	50%		No	Yes	

A/c no 002; Image: Moong

A/c no 0064; Image: Moong

Crop: Moong

Trials on farmer's field (064)

Trial plot no. /pass book no.	Crop name and variety	No. of plants stand	% of plants with flower	Any disease observed in plants so far	Water logging	Contact with scientist	Other vulnerable factor
0064	Ragi Madhopur haat	85%	40%	no	No	yes	no

Ac no 0064; Image Ragi

Harvesting Report:

**Report
Pod and Harvesting
Kharif Season
BIHAR**

Crop: Ghaghra

Trials on farmer's field (001,002, 005, 064)

Trail plot no/passbook no.	Crop name variety name	Pod appearing date	Number of seeds per pod	No. of pod in a plant	Any disease observed plants so far	Harvesting of pods date	Quantity (kg) of seed got from trial plot	Color of pod and no of seed in pod	Other vulnerable factor
001	Ghaghra Telwa haat	20/8/22	10-12	20-40	Yes, leaf insect	27/ 9/22	6-7kg	White	No
002	Ghaghra Etwari marandi	24/8/22	10-14	25-45	Yes	29/9/22	3-4kg	White	No
005	Ghaghra sakina bibi	19/8/22	10-12	30-40	Yes	27/9/22	5-6kg	White	No
064	Ghaghra madhopur haat	21/8/22	8-10	30-50	yes	30/9/22	7-9kg	white	No

A/c NO 0064; Image: Ghaghra

A/c no 001; Image: Ghaghra

A/c no 005; Image Ghaghra

A/c no 002; Image: Ghaghra

Crop:

Trials on farmer's field (Jiva Soren's Farm 002)

Trail plot no/pass book no002	Crop name variety name	Pod appearing date	Number of seeds per pod	No. of pod in a plants	Any disease observed plants so far	Harvesting of pods date	Quantity (kg) of seed got from trial plot	Color of pod and no of seed in pod	Other vulnerable factor
Trial 1	Arhar (Ratan)	0	0	0	yes	0	0		Yes rain
Trial 2	Grpundnut .jiwa	0	0	0		0	0		
Trial 3	Urad (T9)	25/8/2022	4-6	45-55		7/10/2022	300gm	Black	
Trial 4	Moong (IPM 2-3)	20/8/2022	4-6	60-65		2/10/2022	500	Black	
Trial 5	Ghaghra. Etwari	21/8/2022	8-10	50-60		2/10/2022	400gm	White	
Trial 6	Maize, sarikar	24/8/2022	430	1		6/10/2022	2kg	White/red	

Trial 6: Image: Maize	

Crop: Maize

Trials on farmer's field (001, 002, 064,005, 012)

Trail plot no/passbook no.	Crop name variety name	Pod appearing date	Number of seeds per pod	No. of pod in a plant	Any disease observed plants so far	Harvesting of pods date	Quantity (kg) of seed got from trial plot	Color of pod and no of seed in pod	Other venerable factor
001	Maize (Kanchan)	11/8/22	410	1	NO	29/ 9/22	60-70kg	RED	No
002	Maize (sarokar)	13/8/22	380	1	NO	26/9/22	50-60kg	Red	No
064	Maize (madhopur haat)	14/8/22	300	1	NO	28/9/22	40-45kg	White	No
005	Maize (telwa haat)	17/8/22	285	1	NO	25/9/22	30-35kg	Yellow	No
012	Maize (madhopur)	14/8/22	295	1	NO	22/9/22	30-35kg	Red	No

A/c No. 001; Image; Maize

A/c No 002; Image: Maize

A/c No. 0064; Image: Maize

A/c No 005; Image: Maize

A/c No. 0012; Image: Maize

Crop: Arhar, Moong, White Kudrum, Ghagra, Maize, Pearl Millet

Trials on farmer's field (Farmer Karmeli Kisku)

Trail plot no/passbook no005	Crop name variety name	Pod appearing date	Number of seeds per pod	No. of pod in a plant	Any disease observed plants so far	Harvesting of pods date	Quantity (kg) of seed got from trial plot	Color of pod and no of seed in pod	Other venerable factor
Trial 1	Arhar, LRG 41	0	0	0	yes	0	0	0	Yes rain
Trial 2	moong .jiwa	22/8/2022	4-6	40-45		28/9/2022	250gm	black	
Trial 3	White kudrum, telwa	0	0	0		0	0		
Trial 4	Ghaghra ,sakina	26/8/2022	8-10	50-55		1/10/2022	300gm	white	
Trial 5	Maize telwa	20/8/2022	280-350	1		2/10/2022	2kg	White/red	
Trial 6	Bajra madhopur	0	0	0		0	0		

Crop: Moong

Trials on farmer's field (001,002, 005, 064)

Trail plot no/passbook no.	Crop name variety name	Pod appearing date	Number of seeds per pod	No. of pod in a plants	Any disease observed plants so far	Harvesting of pods date	Quantity (kg) of seed got from trial plot	Color of pod and no of seed in pod	Other venerable factor
001	Moong ipm25	19/8/22	5-8	50-60	Yes leaf insect	26/9/22	7kg	black	No
002	Moong, (ipm2-3)	23/8/22	5-8	45-55	„	24/9/22	9kg	„	No
005	Moong, (jiwa soren)	14/8/22	4-6	30-40	„	28/9/22	5kg	Black	No
0064	Moong (tuka besra)	12/8/22	4-6	30-40	„	29/9/22	6kg	„	No

A/c no 005; Image: Moong

A/c no 0064; Image: Moong

Crop: Ragi

Trials on farmer's field (064)

Trail plot no/passbook no.	Crop name variety name	Pod appearing date	Number of seeds per pod	No. of pod in a plant	Any disease observed plants so far	Harvesting of pods date	Quantity (kg) of seed got from trial plot	Color of pod and no of seed in pod	Other venerable factor
0064	Madhopur haat, Ragi	18/9/22	50-80	1-2	No	6/10/22	15kg	Bura	no

A/c No. 064; Image: Ragi (Finger Millet)
